

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17409644

Consumer Education Awareness of Prepaid Meter Users and Satisfaction among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study examined Consumer Education awareness of prepaid meter users and satisfaction among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise (SME) operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. Three specific objectives guided the study, three research questions were posed and three hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlation research design was adopted and conducted in Port Harcourt metropolis. The population of the study was 3,006 registered SME operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. Sample size of 353 respondents was determined through stratified sampling technique using Taro-Yamane formula. Data collection was done through the use of questionnaire instruments. The instruments were titled “Consumer Education Awareness on Prepaid Meter Usage Questionnaire (CEAPMUQ) for the independent variables and Consumer Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage Questionnaire (ConSaPMUQ)” for the dependent variables. The instruments were validated by three experts; two in Business Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation. Cronbach Alpha was used to establish the reliability coefficient. The obtained Cronbach’s values were 0.88 and 0.71 for CEAPMUQ and ConSaPMUQ respectively. Three hundred and fifty-three (353) copies of questionnaire were distributed out of which only 281 copies were retrieved for collation and analysis of data. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and to test the hypotheses as well. Findings from the study revealed that there is a low positive relationship between the awareness level of consumer rights and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among SME operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. Also, the study further indicated that a very low positive relationship exists between the level of awareness of consumer obligations and their satisfaction on prepaid meter usage. Based on the findings, the study recommended amongst others that the Nigerian Electricity Regulation Commission (NERC) should publicize the consumer rights on prepaid meter usage more adequately to create more awareness on these rights among SME operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Keywords: Consumer Education, Awareness, Prepaid Meter Usage, Consumer Rights and Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Consumers are the primary players in Consumer Education as both their consumer behaviour and spending pattern directly impact the economy of a nation. Consumer spending could be seen as the engine

of economic growth that affects a nation's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). It is pertinent to note that reduced consumer spending will result in low economic growth as there will be less cash flow and investments. Therefore, consumers need to be educated and given full information about various market dynamics and products to help them make sound purchase and investment decisions. Consumer Education guarantees consumer protection and allows them to make wise decisions in the use of resources at their disposal. The adoption of Consumer Education is not limited to a particular sector as it could be used in all sectors but for the purpose of this study, its focus is on the Power sector. The power sector is one vital area where consumers need to be adequately informed due to its economic impact.

A country's economic well-being depends heavily on the availability of electricity as most aspects of human social life revolve around it on daily basis. Alao, Jimoh and Obadiora (2022) opined that the growth of a nation's infrastructure fuels the development of its people and activities as the advancement of nations wouldn't have been possible without electricity. Electricity has invaded every facet of human lives. People need electricity to run infrastructures that makes lives easier, productive and efficient. Civilization has come to the point where human being cannot think of anything without electricity. In Nigeria, Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCo) are saddled with the task of supplying electricity to consumers. The DisCo supply the electricity and in turn bill the consumer.

Basically, there are two most prevalent types of electricity billing system in Nigeria and around the world – the postpaid and prepaid metering systems. Most households according to Aribisala and Mohammed (2021) have predominantly been subjected to postpaid billing up until lately that there has been a significant shift towards the prepaid metering system. This shift is due to the fact that with the postpaid metering system, users are billed, and monthly payments are made based on the overall usage which means that service takes precedence over payment. Alao, Jimoh and Obadiora (2022) buttressed that postpaid metering system enable consumers to pay after they have already consumed the electricity. Meaning that meter readers takes the meter reading and bill will be sent to the consumer. This practice witnessed a lot of complaints from the consumers of the services rendered by electricity distribution company. The postpaid metering billing were sometimes outrageous as the bills were estimated without a functional reading of meters on the precise consumption. Other postpaid billing difficulties as identified by Fasoranti, Alimi and Ofonyetu (2022), include meter reading errors resulting in payment irregularities, inaccessible meter readings causing meter readers to assume and guess. Also, problems associated with the connectivity were not left out.

On the other hand, just as the name implies, the prepaid metering system requires that consumers pay for electricity before consumption. The users can choose the amount that they need according to their usage and the digital screen also allows them to monitor their usage. The users can use their monthly recharge as a limit to their electricity usage or the units purchased can be topped up throughout the month if necessary (Jimoh, Kayode, & Obadiora, 2022).

Consumer Education and its Importance

Consumer Education has been defined in a variety of ways, particularly in consumer behavioural studies. Consumer Education according to Alao, Jimoh and Obadiora (2022), entails the development of skills, concepts and understanding to assist consumers in achieving maximum satisfaction and maximizing the use of their human and material resources. Pajari and Harmoinen (2019), opined that Consumer education could be seen as a process of developing and enhancing skills and knowledge to make informed and well-reasoned choices that take societal values and objectives into account. Nnubia and Wagbara (2022) posited that consumer education is the programme that gives the consumers an understanding of their rights that concerns food purchases. As this provides the knowledge the consumers acquire that makes them to understand their rights, know what to buy, when to buy, where to buy from and how to make use of the products bought and the services. Consumer education studies the services in marketing and management of products. It emphasizes on the importance of presenting information about goods and services, and their providers in order to improve basic and in-depth knowledge for using information in a quality service perspective (Jimoh, Kayode & Obadiora, 2022).

Consumer Education creates consumer's awareness about the expiry dates, purchase and consumption planning of good and services (Solis & Krajewska, 2020). Consumers need to receive education about the usage of any goods and services to enhance full utilization of the commodity. Consumer education promotes decision-making in regards to the choice of available products or services as it helps to avoid disaster. For instance, if consumers are educated on the use of certain drugs in a particular way, and are also warned of the danger of using that same drugs in combination with other drugs. This will not only inform the consumer but will also save the consumer and the lives of other people from danger. With this, consumers lower their perceived risk after gathering a lot of information about a product based on the available options. This in turn is highly appreciated by the consumers themselves.

Usman (2022) posits that consumer education is the process of assisting people to acquire the correct information and understanding that will help them make wise decision when purchasing goods and services. It is an aspect that enlighten consumers on what, where, when, how and how much to buy and use what they have bought. On the usage of products, consumers can also ask for a demonstration of its usage. Others are:

- a) Consumer Education offers the consumer full information of marketing conditions like various sources of purchasing a particular commodity, from where to get cheap and best goods. The shops that provide additional facilities and the latest products. All these information enables the consumer in taking right decisions regarding shopping.
- b) Familiarizes the consumer with various standards of standardization and their makings.
- c) Familiarizes the consumer with various acts enacted by the government from time to time. This helps the consumer in getting satisfaction by proper utilization of his money and leads to better living and standard.
- d) Familiarizes the consumer with problems which he or she faces while making purchases. This education inculcates the logical viewpoint in him.
- e) Consumer Education ensures that companies are held accountable by government agencies and the consumers that use their products and services.
- f) It helps consumers understand their rights and become active participants in the buying process.
- g) Provides the public with information it needs on goods and services.
- h) Motivates consumers to provide feedback that can be used to improve the quality of products and services.
- i) Helps a person in making proper purchase and enables the consumer in making selection.
- j) Keeps economy growing as it holds companies accountable for what they sell.
- k) Makes people aware of the quality of goods and services they are purchasing.
- l) It gives consumers control over their purchases (Sasikumar & Usha, 2014).

During the 2022 World Consumer Rights Day in Abuja, Udegbonam (2022), stated that Adeniyi Adebayo, the Minister of Industry, Trade and Investment speaking on behalf of the Federal government urged Nigerians to defend their rights as consumers and should stand against exploitation by firms and service providers. Stressing that as a consumer, you should be aware of your rights to safety, be informed, be heard and seek redress against any form of exploitative service. With this charge given to Nigerians, one will begin to wonder if the rights of consumers are actually protected?

It is pertinent to say that informing the consumers about goods and services makes the consumer to be educated. This practice is not only obtainable in Nigeria but it is also seen in other parts of the world. Saikumar and Usha (2014) stated that the United Nations Organization's Guidelines and the consumer protection Act – 1986 of India undoubtedly states about six rights of consumers. They are:

- i. Right to safety
- ii. Right to information
- iii. Right to choice
- iv. Right to be heard
- v. Right to redress
- vi. Right to consumer education.

In Nigeria, the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), as an agency established by the Electric Power Sector Reform (EPSR) Act 2005 introduced a set of consumer rights, obligations and protection laws to curb the excesses of electricity operators and to ensure they provide quality service to customers. Unfortunately, many electricity consumers are not aware of these rights thus allowing the electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos) to entrench their abusive practices against them. It is therefore pertinent for consumers to know what their rights are under the law so that they can effectively insist on them in their dealings with the service providers. Below is an overview of the rights, obligations and protection laws set out by NERC.

Electricity Consumer Rights

1. All customers have a right to electricity supply in a safe and reliable manner. This presupposes that service providers are under obligation to ensure their services or equipment do not endanger the safety, health, life and property of consumers.
2. All customers have a right to a properly installed and functional meter. Electricity consumers are entitled to a functional meter installed in their property. Initially, the electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos) were mandated to ensure consumers were metered. However, with the recent licensing of Meter Asset Providers (MAP), consumers are required to bear the financial burden of procuring the prepaid meters from the meter vendors whose responsibility is to fund, procure and install meters on behalf of the DisCo in their coverage area.
3. All new electricity connection must be done strictly based on metering before connection. That is, no new customer should be connected by a DisCo without a meter first being installed at the premises.
4. All customers have a right to transparent electricity billing. Electricity consumers' bills should be based on actual energy consumed, not estimated billing. But where estimated billing is to be applied, it should not exceed what a customer could possibly have consumed within the billing period. For instance, the estimates for unmetered customers must be reasonable when compared with metered customers occupying similar property or based on load assessment of their premises. In the case of customers whose meters are faulty, the estimated usage should be based on the property's previous usage pattern.
5. All un-metered customers should be issued with electricity bills strictly based on NERC's estimated billing methodology. This is to say that for customers who are unmetered, their billing should not be done arbitrarily but must follow NERC's estimated billing methodology.
6. Customers have the right to contest any electricity bill. It is within the right of any electricity consumer to contest any bill they believe does not reflect their consumption. They can request a review of their bill, in which case, the DisCo will have to carry out a load assessment at the billing address to determine how the bill should be adjusted if necessary.
7. Any un-metered customer who is disputing his or her estimated bill has the right not to pay the disputed bill, but pay only the last undisputed bill as the contested bill goes through the dispute resolution process of NERC. When a bill is in dispute, a customer is not obligated to pay the amount on it. He can pay the amount on the last undisputed bill until the dispute is resolved.
8. All customers have a right to refund when over-billed. DisCos are required to refund excess money paid by customers where it has been proven that they were over-billed. Such refunds may not be made in cash but credited into the customers' accounts for subsequent payments.
9. All customers have a right to be properly informed and educated on electricity service. The service providers are obligated to provide consumers with information on their services as required, particularly when such has a direct impact on the consumers. They should not be left in the dark on what is going on.
10. It is the customer's right to be notified in writing ahead of disconnection of electricity service by the DisCo serving the customer in line with NERC's guidelines. DisCos rarely comply with this guideline because consumers do not insist on their rights by taking appropriate steps to seek redress. Disconnections are done arbitrarily and this is wrong. A customer who is disconnected without a written notice can sue the service provider or file a complaint with NERC. If convicted, the DisCo will be made to pay compensation to the affected customer.

11. All customers have a right to file complaints and to the prompt investigation of complaints. Any aggrieved customer has a right to file a complaint which should be investigated within fifteen (15) working days from the date the complaint was submitted. Unfortunately, most consumers merely grumble but never file complaints when their rights are violated.
12. All complaints on electricity supply and other billing issues are to be sent to the nearest business unit of the DisCo serving the customer. Electricity customers can file a complaint at the business unit of the service provider. But when a complaint is not satisfactorily addressed, the customer has a right to escalate such to the NERC Forum Office within the coverage area of the DisCo.
13. Customers have the right to appeal the decision of the NERC Forum Office by writing a petition to the Commission. Electricity consumers whose cases have been determined by NERC Forum Office can appeal to the Commission itself if they are not satisfied with the forum's decision.
14. It is not the responsibility of electricity customer or community to buy, replace or repair electricity transformers, poles and related equipment used in the supply of electricity. Transformers, poles and related equipment used in the supply of electricity belong to the DisCos and should, therefore, take responsibility for their supply, maintenance, repair, or replacement. It is not the responsibility of the customer or community. However, with the recent licensing of Meter Assets Providers (MAP) across the country, consumers are required to pay for prepaid meters.

Obligations of Electricity Consumers

Rights come with responsibilities. For consumers to exercise the above rights, they must understand and comply with the obligations of electricity consumers as issued by NERC as below.

1. Pay bills for electricity consumed
2. Provide requirements for connection as stipulated by NERC and DisCo. This implies that a customer requiring connection to their premises shall be responsible for providing connection materials while DisCo shall be responsible for the connection from the available supply to the customer's metering point – Section 12(2).
3. Vigilant protection of electrical installations
4. Cordiality towards electricity workers
5. Customer compliance with the requirements of the Distribution code
6. Pay for electricity used within the stipulated time frame
7. Ensure receipt of monthly electricity bills if not on prepaid meters and lodge a complaint to the DisCo serving you should you not get your bills
8. Ensure that metering and other electrical equipment within your premises belonging to the DisCo are not tampered with, or by-passed
9. Notify the DisCo serving you of any tampering or bypass of electricity installations
10. Notify the DisCo serving you of any outstanding electricity bill before moving into new premises

Protection Laws of Electricity Consumers

According to Ojoko and Ojoko (2023), opined that the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) on the 26th of July 2021 issued a Consultation Paper on the Review of Customer Protection Regulations in the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry (NESI). The aim of the Consultation was to elicit the view of NESI stakeholders in the proposed overhauling of the different regulations which had created various customer rights in the NESI. The placement of these rights in different NERC regulations, rather than one single document, had created an awareness deficit among customers of the Electricity Distribution Companies (EDC), leading to a situation where customer rights were routinely abused by EDC thereby taking advantage of their ignorance.

The result of the wide-ranging consultation process drew input of reputable organizations such as the Nigerian Electricity Consumers Advocacy Network (NECAN), Powerup Nigeria, and other electricity advocacy initiatives and this gave birth to the Consumer Protection Regulations (CPR) 2023, which was passed into law by NERC on 29th March 2023. Some of the laws are stated as follows:

- a) A debt left by the previous customer cannot be transferred to a new customer – Section 29(3). The DisCo shall be responsible for recovering the debt left by a previous tenant of any premises.

- b) A new customer shall notify the DisCo on the first day of moving into the premises. The customer will only be liable for payment of bills from the date of reconnection (which would be the day he or she moved in) – Section 29(5).
- c) The only recognized customer of a DisCo is the registered owner of the property or any person authorized by the owner to use and settle electricity bills on the premises – Section 29(6).
- d) There is now a clear distinction between the registered owner and customer of electricity for the purposes of billing and settlement – Section 29(7). The registered owner is the person in whose name the electricity bill is written (which is usually the owner of the premises), while the customer of electricity is the occupant of the premises.
- e) Complaints of meter accuracy and reconciliation of bills shall be resolved within billing cycle of one month (30 days) – Section 43(7).
- f) If the complaint is not resolved within the first 15 days, the DisCo shall write to the customer to explain the reason(s) for the delay and request for no more than 15 additional days to resolve the issue, except the resolution, by its nature, requires as longer period – Section 43(8).
- g) A dissatisfied customer can refer the outcome of the resolution, or the DisCo's failure to respond to his complaint, to the Forum office at the end of 30 days' period – Section 43(9).
- h) Where a prepaid meter (called a prepayment meter in the new regulation) is programmed to operate in credit mode, the customer shall be notified prior to the installation of the meter and the DisCo shall be allowed to recover for the negative meter reading at the next vending –Section 62(4).
- i) If a prepayment meter is reading in credit mode without being programmed to do so, and without the knowledge of the customer, the customer shall not be billed for the negative meter reading – Section 62(5).
- j) Where the prepayment meter is reading in a credit mode without being programmed to do so, and without the knowledge of the customer, the meter shall be considered faulty and shall be replaced in line with the Distribution Meter Code (DMC) – Section 62(6).
- k) Where a prepayment meter is pre-programmed with pre-set energy credit, the DisCo shall inform the customer of the energy unit credits to be recovered at the next vending
Section 62(7).

Merits and Demerits of Prepaid Meters in Nigeria

Orukpe and Agbontaen (2014) identified the merits as follows:

1. The introduction of prepaid meters in Nigeria has helped the environment because tones of papers have been saved in printing of bills.
2. Consumers saves more using prepaid meters than in postpaid billing system.
3. It helps consumers to monitor their energy usage and make reductions in energy consumption and carbon emissions as well.
4. It helps supplier have a better knowledge of the state of their power networks
5. Government can invest in the manufacture of these meters in Nigeria instead of having to import them.

Makanjuola, Shoewu, Akinyemi and Ajose (2015), enumerated the demerits as:

1. Inadequate vending infrastructure: One of the major obstacles militating against the deployment of prepaid meters is that some areas lacked the vending infrastructure, as a result, prepaid meters could not be deployed. Vending infrastructure, simply comprises of software built into a Pre-Payment Meter (PPM) Master Station which automatically allows for vending often on vouchers or on electronic media. Vending in itself is the capability of a point of sale device to generate the prepaid token and conclude the associated prepayment transaction.
2. Lack of Local Manufacturers: The absence of competent local meter manufacturers is considered a critical element that accounts for the delay in meter procurement.
3. Corruption: Typical of the entire geo-political zone, the allegations of corruption and extortion were raised against some unscrupulous DisCo staff where customers complained of being extorted by a

certain contractor who was neither a licensee of NERC nor a contractor to DisCo in installing transformer in the community.

Some related studies have been done in other parts of the country and outside Nigeria on evaluating the satisfaction of the use of prepaid meters. These include Boadu (2016); Rabbani, Muaz, Sakib & Tanvir (2020); Aribisala & Mohammed (2021); Alao, Jimoh & Obadiora, (2022); Fasoranti, Alimi & Ofonyetu (2022). Due to limited literature available to the researcher, it does not appear that any such studies have been done on consumer education awareness and prepaid meter users satisfaction among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. This implies that there is need to examine empirically and document the awareness level of consumer education on prepaid meter usage and their level of satisfaction among small and medium-scale enterprises operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, there have been a lot of complaints by consumers of electricity on the use of the postpaid billing system by Electricity Distribution Companies (EDC) in Nigeria. Amongst these complaints is the issuance of estimated outrageous bills without a functional reading of meters to ascertain the exact amount of electricity consumed (Alao, Jimoh & Obadiora, 2022). As a result of this, the Federal Government in collaboration with the Central Bank of Nigeria flagged off the National Mass Metering Programme (NMMP) in October, 2020 to supply consumers with prepaid meters. The NMMP was to ensure a service reflective tariff and to fast-track the closure of the end-users metering gap in the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry (Akintayo, 2023).

The Federal Government commenced the mass deployment of about six million meters across the country to enhance consumers' satisfaction, although, it was observed that some of the electricity consumers were opposed to being metered (Obi, 2022). Possibly, this could be to avoid paying the exact cost for the electricity consumed by them and not considering the satisfaction the use of prepaid metering system may offer them. In line with this, the Nigerian Electricity Regulation Commission (NERC) in 2021 ordered EDC to disconnect any electricity consumer who rejects the prepaid meter. Is it possible that the rejection or non-acceptance of the prepaid meters by some electricity consumers maybe traceable to their limited knowledge about the use of prepaid meters, particularly their rights, obligations and the protection laws provided under the prepaid metering scheme? Could their awareness level of Consumer Education correlate with their satisfaction on the use of prepaid meter in Port Harcourt metropolis?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine Consumer Education Awareness of Prepaid Meter Users and Satisfaction among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between the awareness level of consumer rights and their satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.
2. Examine the relationship between the awareness level of consumer obligations and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.
3. Examine the relationship between the awareness level of consumer protection laws and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does the awareness level of consumer rights relate to the satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis?
2. How does the awareness level of consumer obligations relate to the satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis?
3. How does the awareness level of consumer protection laws relate to the satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between the mean response of the awareness of consumer rights and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.
2. There is no significant relationship between the mean response of the awareness of consumer obligations and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.
3. There is no significant relationship between the mean response of the awareness of consumer protection laws and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the correlational research design. The study area was in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Port Harcourt metropolis in this study comprised of Port Harcourt City Local Government Area (PHALGA), Obio/Akpor Local Government Area (OBALGA), Oyibo Local Government Area (OYILGA), and Eleme Local Government (ELELGA) of Rivers State. The population consisted of 3,006 registered operators of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises. A sample size of 353 respondents was determined through Stratified sampling technique using Taro Yamane formular. Two structured questionnaire instruments were used for data collection and were titled “Consumer Education Awareness on Prepaid Meter Usage Questionnaire (CEAPMUQ) and “Consumer Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage Questionnaire (ConSaPMUQ)”. The CEAPMUQ instrument was structured on 4-point rating scale of Very High Level (VHL – 4 points), High Level (HL – 3 points), Moderate Level (ML – 2 points) and Low Level (LL – 1 point) while the ConSaPMUQ was structured as Highly Satisfied (HS – 4 points), Satisfied (S – 3 points), Dissatisfied (D – 2 points) and Highly Dissatisfied (HD – 1 point).

The research instruments were subjected to face and content validity by three experts, two in Business Education and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation all from Rivers State University. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha and these yielded reliability coefficients of 0.88 and 0.71 for CEAPMUQ and ConSaPMUQ respectively.

Copies of the instruments were administered with the aid of research assistants. Out of the 353 copies of the instruments administered, 281 were retrieved respectively for data analysis as 72 copies were not retrieved representing 20 percent. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions and also used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 significant level. The decision for the hypotheses was that obtained P-value greater than the level of significance of 0.05 was accepted and where otherwise, it was rejected. Also, the decision for the research questions was based on the (r) coefficient shown in the table below:

Table 1: Result Interpretation of Correlation Coefficient (r) Analysis

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
± 1.00	Perfect Positive or Negative Correlation
± .90 - ± .99	Very high Positive or Negative Correlation
± .70 - ± .89	High Positive or Negative Correlation
± .50 - ± .69	Moderate Positive or Negative Correlation
± .30 - ± .49	Low Positive or Negative Correlation
± .10 - ± .29	Very low Positive or Negative Correlation
± .00 - ± .09	Zero Correlation or Negligible Positive or Negative Correlation

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *How does the awareness level of consumer rights relate to the satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis?*

Table 2: Respondents Rating of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Awareness Level of Consumer Rights and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt Metropolis

		Consumer Rights	Con. Satisfaction	Remark
Consumer Rights	Pearson Correlation	1	.334**	Low Positive Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	281	281	
Con. Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.334**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	281	281	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in Table 2 showed that ($r = 0.33$) indicating that a low positive relationship exists between the awareness level of consumer rights and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise (SME) operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. This means that an increase in the awareness of consumer rights on prepaid meter usage will lead to an increase in the satisfaction level of prepaid meter usage among SME operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Research Question 2: *How does the awareness level of consumer obligations relate to the satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis?*

Table 3: Respondents Rating of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Awareness Level of Consumer Obligations and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt Metropolis

		Consumer Obligations	Con. Satisfaction	Remark
Consumer Obligations	Pearson Correlation	1	.251**	Very Low Positive Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	281	281	
Con. Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.251**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	281	281	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in Table 2 showed that ($r = 0.25$) indicating that a very low positive relationship exists between the awareness level of consumer obligations and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise (SME) operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. This means that an increase in the level of awareness of consumer obligations of prepaid meter usage will lead to an increase in the derived satisfaction of consumers on prepaid meter usage among SME operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Research Question 3: *How does the awareness level of consumer protection laws relate to the satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis?*

Table 4: Respondents Rating of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Awareness Level of Consumer Protection Laws and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt Metropolis

		Consumer Protection Laws	Con. Satisfaction	Remark
Consumer Protection Laws	Pearson Correlation	1	.205**	Very Low Positive Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	281	281	
Con. Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.205**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	281	281	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in Table 2 showed that ($r = 0.21$) indicating that a very low positive relationship exists between the awareness of consumer protection laws and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise (SME) operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. This means that an increase in the awareness of consumer protection laws on prepaid meter usage will lead to an increase in the satisfaction of consumers on prepaid meter usage among SME operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the mean response of the awareness of consumer rights and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Table 5: Analysis of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Awareness Level of Consumer Rights and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt Metropolis

		Consumer Rights	Con. Satisfaction	Remark
Consumer Rights	Pearson Correlation	1	.334**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	281	281	
Con. Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.334**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	281	281	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in Table 5 revealed that the obtained P-value of 0.00 is less than the significance level of 0.05 ($P = 0.00 < 0.05$), hence the hypothesis was rejected. The analysis is an indication that there is a significant relationship between the awareness of consumer rights and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the mean response of the awareness of consumer obligations and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Table 6: Analysis of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Awareness Level of Consumer Obligations and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt Metropolis

		Consumer Obligations	Con. Satisfaction	Remark
Consumer Obligations	Pearson Correlation	1	.251**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	281	281	
Con. Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.251**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	281	281	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in Table 6 revealed that the obtained P-value of 0.00 is less than the significance level of 0.05 ($P = 0.00 < 0.05$), hence the hypothesis was rejected. The analysis of having a P-value less than the alpha level of significance is an indication that there is a significant relationship between the awareness of consumer obligations and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the mean response of the awareness of consumer protection laws and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Table 7: Analysis of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Awareness Level of Consumer Protection Laws and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise Operators in Port Harcourt Metropolis

		Consumer Protection Laws	Con. Satisfaction	Remark
Consumer Protection Laws	Pearson Correlation	1	.205**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	281	281	
Con. Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.205**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	281	281	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in Table 7 indicated that the obtained P-value of 0.00 is less than the significance level of 0.05 ($P = 0.00 < 0.05$), hence the hypothesis was rejected. This is therefore an indication that there is a significant relationship between the awareness of consumer protection laws and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of findings was done based on the research questions and formulated hypotheses.

Awareness Level of Consumer Rights and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage

Research Question one sought to determine how the awareness level of consumer rights relate to the satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. The findings of this study revealed that a low positive relationship exists between the awareness level of consumer rights and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and

Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. Being that the relationship is low shows that the response of the consumers on the awareness level of consumer right is not high. This is to say that if there is an increase in the awareness of consumer rights on prepaid meter usage, there will also be an increase in the satisfaction level on prepaid meter usage and this will in turn increase the relationship between the two variables. In other words, the more the consumers are exposed to knowing their rights, the more their awareness level will increase as well as their satisfaction level. These consumers need to be well informed of their rights on prepaid meter usage. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Alao, Jimoh and Obadiora (2022) who, in a study to determine Customer Education and Satisfaction of prepaid meter usage in Nigeria Electricity Distribution Company found that there is need for proper sensitization of electricity customers before introducing prepaid meters to them. The researcher examined electricity customers on the following rights: right to properly installed and functional meter, right to electricity supply in a safe and reliable manner, right to transparent electricity billing on the prepaid meter and so on. Responses to all of these rights by the respondents, showed that not all of them are aware of the existence of these rights.

The findings on the hypothesis, showed that there is a significant relationship between the awareness of consumer rights and satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Awareness Level of Consumer Obligations and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage

Findings from research question two showed that a very low positive relationship exists between the awareness level of consumer obligations and their satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. This means that the level of awareness of consumer obligations on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis is low. Hence, there is need for an increase in the awareness of consumer obligations on prepaid meter usage to also increase their satisfaction level. The achievement of this feat can be made possible by aggressive sensitization. Also, findings of the hypothesis showed that there is a significant relationship between the awareness of consumer obligations on prepaid meter usage and their level of satisfaction among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. However, the study indicated that the consumers are relatively satisfied with the prepaid meter usage. The researcher therefore, examined their level of satisfaction based on the following: the ease they have in recharging the prepaid meter, the accuracy of their prepaid meter reading, the transparency in the billing system provided by the service providers, the mode of payment, their ability to monitor their consumption and the fact that there are no meter readers coming to their premises. Agreeing with the views of Boadu (2016), Rabbani, Muaz, Sakib and Tanvir (2020) and Aribisala and Mohammed (2021), the satisfaction of electricity customers is based on the benefits of prepaid meter usage as this include carefulness with energy consumption, minimal cost, more power supply, ability to recharge credit units with ease as well as having no reconnection fee to pay as there are no meter readers coming to their premises. Also, their findings revealed that seventy-five percent of consumers prefer prepaid meter to postpaid meter due to the satisfaction they had on prepaid meter usage.

Awareness Level of Consumer Protection Laws and Satisfaction on Prepaid Meter Usage

Research question three sought to examine how the awareness level of consumer protection laws relate to the satisfaction level on prepaid meter usage of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. Findings indicated that a very low positive relationship existed between the level of consumer protection laws and their satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis. This means that the level of awareness of consumer protection laws on prepaid meter usage is low. It goes to show that if there is an increase in the awareness level of consumer protection laws, there will be an increase in their level of satisfaction on prepaid meter usage. Hence, there is need for prepaid meter users among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt to be sensitized to make them to be fully aware of the protection laws on prepaid meter usage. Also, the findings of the hypothesis showed that there is a significant relationship between the

awareness of consumer protection laws and their satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis.

CONCLUSION

The study on Consumer Education awareness level and their satisfaction on prepaid meter usage among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis indicated that there is a positive relationship between the variables. However, the degree of their relationship varies as the relationship between the awareness level of consumer rights and satisfaction indicated a low positive relationship. Whereas, the relationship between the awareness of consumer obligations, protection laws and their level of satisfaction indicated a very low positive relationship. But on the awareness level of consumer protection laws, both groups indicated to a low level. Conclusively, the prepaid meter users among Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators in Port Harcourt metropolis should be sensitized on the awareness of consumer rights, obligations, and the protection laws made available by NERC the more as this increases their satisfaction also.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The awareness of consumer rights on the use of prepaid meter should be adequately publicize by the Nigerian Electricity Regulation Commission (NERC) for Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise (SME) operators for them to be fully aware.
2. Consumer obligations on the use of prepaid meter among SME operators should be adequately made publicly by Electricity Distribution Companies in collaboration with the Nigerian Electricity Regulation Commission to create more awareness.
3. There should be adequate sensitization of the existence of consumer protection laws on the use of prepaid meter by the Nigerian Electricity Regulation Commission and Electricity Distribution Companies among SME operators to create more awareness.
4. Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise operators should accept and embrace prepaid meter usage as these prepaid meter users are satisfied.

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